

پاکستان کے دینی تعلیمی اداروں میں ادب الاختلاف کی بطور مضمون تدریس ضرورت و اہمیت

TEACHING “MANNERS OF DISAGREEMENT” AS A SUBJECT IN PAKISTANI INSTITUTES OF ISLAMIC EDUCATION NEED & IMPORTANCE

Dr. Abdul Qadir (ORCID ID: 0000-0002-0107-9676)

Assistant Professor, Department of Islamic Studies, Bahria University, Karachi.

Dr. Muhammad Iftikhar Ahmed (ORCID ID: 0000-0002-2128-6963)

Adjunct Faculty Member, Institute of Business Management, Karachi.

Dr. Sajjad Ahmed (ORCID ID: 0000-0002-4442-4871)

Assistant Professor, College Education Department, Government of Sindh.

ABSTRACT

It is an undeniable fact that our society has intolerance for disagreements, be it in social issues, political issues, or religious issues which make it very difficult to give opinion on debatable issues. Although we face it in almost every filed, but this intolerance is normally more intensive in religious matters. Teaching Manners of Disagreement can play an important role in decreasing this problem. The classical term used for “Manners of Disagreement” is Adab-ul-Ikhtilaf and classical literature is also available on the subject. This paper is an effort to study the curriculums of major Pakistani religious institutions and to find out the level of the content on the subject taught in these institutions. Recommendations will be made for inclusion of this important subject in their curriculum and different levels of their degree programs will also be suggested in which the inclusion of this subject will be more useful.

Keywords: Disagreement, Religious Institutions, Adab-ul-Ikhtilaf, Islamic Education.

کلیدی الفاظ: ادب الاختلاف، دینی تعلیمی ادارے، مدارس، اسلامی تعلیمات، اختلافی مسائل۔

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.8147556